

A CRITICAL EVALUATION FOR A CLASS OF MICRO-MECHANICS MODELS*

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ABSTRACT

New results are derived for the effective properties of composite materials composed of a continuous matrix phase containing a highly concentrated suspension of rigid spherical inclusions. The resulting analytical forms from several different theoretical micro-mechanics models are found to vary widely and they are assessed with respect to physical significance.

SUMMARY

Micro-mechanical analyses are required to predict the effective properties and failure characteristics of composite materials. The term micro-mechanics implies the use of a model which accounts for explicit interaction at the level of a continuous matrix phase and one or more inclusion phases. There are many theoretical micro-mechanical models which have been developed and applied to predict the effective elastic properties of composite materials, and these will be considered here. Furthermore there have been comparisons of such model predictions with data but this has primarily been done in the range where all of the more reasonable models are within the band of the experimental error and only models containing known errors or the meaningless rule of mixtures show large deviations. Few if any critical evaluations have been offered. The present work is intended to provide a critical evaluation of several of the prominent theoretical micro-mechanics models and this summary is excerpted from a recent work¹ with this objective. The many micro-mechanics models that have been developed for predicting the effective, elastic properties of composite materials admit different forms depending upon whether the case of particulate reinforcement or fiber reinforcement is being considered. Models which have a theoretical basis in either case include the following:

- Differential Method
- Composite Spheres (Cylinders) Model
- Self Consistent Method
- Generalized Self Consistent Method
(Three Phase Model)
- Mori-Tanaka Method

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Although there are many other micro-mechanics models they usually are either of an essentially numerical nature involving series or finite element solutions, or they are of an empirical nature, or finally they involve grossly oversimplifying assumptions. The primary references to the main theoretical models are as follows. The Differential Method has a long and interesting history, but it was most effectively developed and used by Roscoe.² The Composite Spheres Model is due to Hashin.³ The Self Consistent Method is credited to Budiansky⁴ and Hill.⁵ The Generalized Self Consistent Method was formalized by Christensen and Lo⁶ and referred to as the Three Phase Model by them. Finally, the Mori-Tanaka method has had many contributors, but the most recent and simplest derivation of it has been given by Benveniste.⁷

To proceed further it is necessary to decide whether to follow the particulate or fiber reinforced case. The present work will focus primarily upon the particulate case since it is of interest in its own right, and the conclusions found from it project over to the fiber reinforced case. In the area of particulate reinforced composite materials explicit attention will be given to the case of spherical inclusions in a continuous matrix phase. It is with this spherical inclusion case that there exist the most relevant and explicit theoretical forms, as well as the greatest likelihood of finding critical data against which to test the various theories. The case of spherical inclusions can be sub-divided into two major classes

- i) Single Size Spherical Inclusions
- ii) Polydisperse (Size) Spherical Inclusions

The case of single size spherical inclusions have been extensively studied by Frankel and Acrivos⁸ in the form of highly concentrated suspensions of rigid inclusions, in the fluids context, and by Chen and Acrivos⁹ under deformable inclusion conditions in the elastic context. The present work covers the polydisperse case of spherical particle suspensions with isotropic properties.

Within the case of polydisperse suspensions of spherical inclusions, the limiting case is specified by those suspensions which permit full packing with $c \rightarrow 1$, where c is the volume fraction of inclusions. Models which permit $c \rightarrow 1$ are of interest for at least three reasons. Micro-mechanics models which permit $c \rightarrow 1$ are particularly amenable to theoretical treatment and in fact are widely used in theoretical studies. Secondly, these micro-mechanics models giving $c \rightarrow 1$ are appropriate for use in describing practical, polydisperse suspensions involving a gradation of sizes of particles. Thirdly, models allowing $c \rightarrow 1$ can serve as reasonable approximations to the mono-disperse case so long as the concentration is not too large. With the restriction that the models permit the full packing of inclusions and for purposes of rigorous comparison and evaluation, two of the previously mentioned micro-mechanics models must be excluded from consideration. These are the Composite Spheres Model and the Self Consistent Method. The Composite

Spheres Model does not give a solution for the effective shear modulus but rather only for the bulk modulus. It does yield information on bounds for the shear modulus but that is not of relevance here where concern is with explicit predictions rather than bounds. Also, the shear deformation property is the primary concern here for reason to be given next. The Self Consistent Method when applied to multi-phase media does not always cover the full range of volume fraction up to $c \rightarrow 1$. This is true particularly when there is a large mis-match in properties of the two phases, which is the case of primary interest here, for reasons which also will be outlined in the following discussion. Thus, the micro-mechanics models which conform with the requirements stated here are:

Differential Method

Generalized Self Consistent Method

Mori-Tanaka Method

It is these models which will be extensively studied, compared and evaluated in the following work.

Most of the comparisons will concern the shear modulus rather than the corresponding volumetric property. This is because the shear property is much more difficult than the volumetric property to analyse. In the more physically based models the volumetric property is governed by a scalar potential whereas the shear property involves vector potentials. Accordingly it is much easier to bring spurious results into a shear modulus micro-mechanics model than it is for the volumetric property.

It is important to search for and examine the range of behavior where the differences between the various micro-mechanics models are the greatest. As already briefly mentioned, most evaluations involve comparisons of models with data in low volume fraction ranges where the differences between them are not great. To see the greatest differences between the models it is necessary to go to conditions involving concentrated suspensions. Furthermore, the greatest differences between model predictions occur for suspensions that have phases with the greatest mis-match in properties between the matrix and inclusions. The work here therefore focuses upon the suspensions involving perfectly rigid spherical particles under highly concentrated conditions in a continuous matrix phase. This case also will provide the most discriminating means of assessing the models relative to experimental data.

Brief mention should be made of the relationship of direct model predictions for properties with corresponding information upon values of upper and lower bounds for the properties. Bounds have value in several different situations. Certainly bounds are of interest when it is not possible to obtain a direct micro-mechanical solution for the effective property of interest. Also, bounds are of use in testing the direct predictions from

models. If predictions from a particular model violate relevant bounds then the model is useless. If, on the other hand, the predictions from a particular model satisfy the relevant bounds, then essentially no information is gained from the bounds relative to the model. That is the situation in operation here. No further reference need be made to bounds, other than to simply observe that all results given and interpreted here are consistent with all relevant bounds information.

The predictions from the various models are compared under high concentration conditions. This is done through the derivation of asymptotic forms appropriate in the limiting case of high concentration of the rigid spherical inclusion phase. The leading terms in the expansions give the dominant effect under high concentration conditions. The details of these lengthy derivations are given by Christensen¹ and the end results of the derivations will be given here. The dominant terms for the effective shear modulus μ obtained for the Differential Method, the Generalized Self Consistent Method and the Mori-Tanaka Method are given in Table 1 where μ_m is the shear modulus of the matrix phase and c is the volume concentration of the spherical particles.

Table 1. Effective Shear Modulus for a High Concentration Rigid Spherical Inclusion Suspension

	<u>Compressible Matrix</u>	<u>Incompressible Matrix</u>
Differential Method	$\frac{\mu}{\mu_m} \rightarrow \frac{F(v_m)}{(1-c)^2}$	$\frac{\mu}{\mu_m} = \frac{1}{(1-c)^{5/2}}$
Generalized Self Consistent Method	$\frac{\mu}{\mu_m} \rightarrow \frac{f(v_m)}{(1-c)}$	$\frac{\mu}{\mu_m} \rightarrow \frac{27}{16(1-c)^3}$
Mori-Tanaka Method	$\frac{\mu}{\mu_m} \rightarrow \frac{\hat{f}(v_m)}{(1-c)}$	$\frac{\mu}{\mu_m} \rightarrow \frac{5}{2(1-c)}$

All results in Table 1 represent the high concentration leading terms of the corresponding expansions except the result shown for the Differential Method with the incompressible matrix phase which is an exact result valid at all concentrations. The symbols $F(v_m)$ and $f(v_m)$ and $\hat{f}(v_m)$ in Table 1 represent functions of the Poisson's ratio, v_m , of the matrix phase. These forms are known from the solutions given in Ref. 1. For example for $v_m = 1/5$ then $F(v_m) = 1$, $f(v_m) = 2.38$ and $\hat{f}(v_m) = 2$. It is seen from Table 1 that the three micro-mechanics models give drastically different predictions of behavior under high concentration conditions. In the incompressible matrix

case the exponent of the dominant $(1-c)$ term ranges from -1 to -3 causing orders of magnitude differences in predictions under very concentrated conditions. The only cases in Table 1 where the different models give the same order of the $(1-c)$ term is for the Generalized Self Consistent Method and the Mori-Tanaka Method in the Compressible Matrix case. However, even in this case the values of the two functions of Poisson's ratio $f(\nu_m)$ and $\hat{f}(\nu_m)$ in Table 1 can be very different. This difference is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Compressible Case, High Concentration

	$\frac{\mu}{\mu_m} \rightarrow \frac{\text{constant}}{(1-c)}$				
	$\nu_m = 0$	$\nu_m = 1/4$	$\nu_m = 1/3$	$\nu_m = .45$	$\nu_m = 1/2$
Generalized Self Consistent Method Constant	2.05	2.54	3	5.92	∞
Mori-Tanaka Method Constant	1.87	2.05	2.14	2.36	5/2

The fact the constant becomes unbounded for the Generalized Self Consistent Method as $\nu_m \rightarrow 1/2$ is simply a reflection of the fact that in the incompressible case the leading term in the expansion is of higher order than that of $1/(1-c)$ and the problem must be reformulated to get the $1/(1-c)^3$ dependence shown in Table 1.

The results shown in Tables 1 and 2 reveal the fundamental differences between the three micro-mechanics models. In Ref. 1 a detailed comparison is given of the three micro-mechanics models with experimental data. The results are more complex than can be simply stated here, because the full theoretical forms of the models must be used rather than just the asymptotic results shown in Table 1. The comparison with experimental data favors the Generalized Self Consistent Method rather than the other two models; see Ref. 1 for the conditions and limitations of the evaluation. The main qualification of these results is that of the restriction to very concentrated conditions for the suspension. Perhaps it could be argued that this limiting case is too severe and under "normal conditions" all the micro-mechanics models discussed here give reasonable predictions. The difficulty, however, is in defining the term normal conditions since there is no clear dividing line. In this sense then a model that gives reasonable behavior in some cases and unreasonable behavior in other cases is no better than an empirical model. In any case, all models recover dilute behavior adequately, and the major technical problem is to properly model the other extreme of behavior, the concentrated suspension case, as has been considered here.

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